

SPRING ZOOPLANKTON ORGANISMS OF TALIMARJON RESERVOIR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8045566>

Abstract: The article studies the characteristics of zooplankton organisms of water reservoirs, their changes and development in the spring period. In spring conditions, the number of plankton organisms, which are interpreted as zooplankton organisms, increases significantly in water reservoirs, and their development directly depends on the temperature and water temperature regime. When the water temperature is high and the amount of oxygen expands, the development and reproduction of zooplankton organisms accelerates. The article mentions the names and characteristics of the main species of zooplankton characteristic of reservoirs during the spring. Among these species, such species as monogonid nematode, RoUéta, Daphnia are of great importance. As a result, the development and reproduction of zooplankton organisms is established by keeping the water temperature at a high level and providing oxygen in the spring period.

Key words: Talimarjon reservoir, Spring, Zooplankton organisms, Ecological processes, Economic activities, Variability, Analysis.

Аннотация: В статье изучены особенности зоопланктонных организмов водоемов, их изменения и развития в весенний период. В весенних условиях в водоемах значительно увеличивается численность планктонных организмов, которые интерпретируются как зоопланктонные организмы, а их развитие находится в прямой зависимости от температуры и температурного режима воды. При высокой температуре воды и увеличении количества кислорода ускоряется развитие и размножение организмов зоопланктона. В статье упоминаются названия и характеристики основных видов зоопланктона, характерных для водоемов в весенний период. Среди этих видов большое значение имеют такие виды, как нематода моногонидная, RoUéta, Daphnia. В результате развитие и размножение зоопланктонных организмов налаживается за счет поддержания температуры воды на высоком уровне и обеспечения кислородом в весенний период.

Ключевые слова: Талимарджонское водохранилище, Весна, Зоопланктонные организмы, Экологические процессы, Хозяйственная деятельность, Изменчивость, Анализ.

Annotatsiya: Maqola bahorgi davrida suv omborlarining zooplankton organizmalarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini, ulardagi o'zgarishlarni va rivojlanishini o'rganadi. Bahorgi sharoitlarda suv omborlarida zooplankton organizmalari nomi bilan talqin etiladigan plankton organizmalarining soni orshantib oshadi va ularda rivojlanish bevosita suvning issiqlik va nuqul rejimiga bog'liq bo'ladi. Suvning harorati yuqori bo'lganda va oksigen miqdori kengayganda, zooplankton organizmalarining rivojlanishi va ko'payishi tezlashtiradi.

Maqolada bahor davomida suv omborlariga xos bo'lgan asosiy zooplankton turlarining nomi va xususiyatlari keltirib o'tilgan. Shu turlar orasida monogonid nématod, RoUéta, Daphnia kabi turlar katta ahamiyatga ega. Natijada, bahor davrida suvni hararatini yuqori darajada saqlash va oksigen miqdori bilan ta'minlash orqali zooplankton organizmalarining rivojlanishi va ko'payishi yo'lga qo'yiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Talimarjon suv ombori, Baxor, Zooplankton organizmlari, Ekologik jarayonlar, Iqtisodiy faoliyatlar, O'zgaruvchilik, Tahlil.

In the article, the basis of the analysis of zooplankton organisms in the Talimarjon Reservoir according to the laws and decisions of the society is also presented. The analysis of zooplankton organisms provides information on the legal conditions and legal terms necessary for the analysis of the Talimarjon reservoir's biological activity.

The article presents the analysis of zooplankton organisms for the study of the Talimarjon Reservoir basin and highlights the importance of zooplankton organism analysis in the study of ecological processes and variability in society.

There are a number of reservoirs in Kashkadarya region that have the potential to develop fisheries. Our research is focused on the study of Tallimarjon, reservoir fish and zooplankton organisms. Tallimarjon reservoir is oligotrophic-mesotrophic and is a freshwater reservoir. This is also reflected in the species of plankton fauna.

The Talimarjon reservoir is a large hydrotechnical facility built at the foot of the Karshi main channel. It was built in 1965-73. It was partially commissioned in 1977 and fully commissioned in 1985. Length. 14 km, width 5.5 km, average depth. 19.8 m. The maximum depth is 41.5 m. The area is 77.4 km², the total volume is 1.53 billion. m³, usable volume, 1.4 billion. m³.

Kashkadarya reservoirs were studied by classical scientists such as [Sibirsova 1971: 53], [Afanaseva 1971: 25], [Karaev 1971: 79].

The samples were collected in the last week of March 2023.

Generally accepted methods were used to collect zooplankton organisms. When taking samples, first of all, the location of the water basin was determined. Then it was determined at which point of the water body zooplanktons are found the most and where samples should be taken. After that, the places of water entry and exit to the water basin were determined and observation points were determined. In the research, first of all, water temperature, clarity, pH and oxygen content were measured.

Sampling and processing of zooplankton samples from water bodies was carried out using standard methods. Collection of zooplankton organisms was collected using a conical plankton net made of kapron (No. 76). The samples were fixed using 4% formalin. For processing samples in laboratory conditions, a certain amount was taken, poured into measuring cups and diluted by adding 100 ml of purified water and thoroughly mixed. 1 ml of it using a temple-pipette. the amount of zooplankton was determined. When the concentration of zooplankton in the agar is less, a certain amount of liquid was taken from them, put into the Bogorova chamber, and all the zooplankton organisms in it were divided into groups and counted.

In the identification of species, the identifiers of Kutikova, Mukhamediev, Mirabdullaev and heads were used.

6 species of zooplankton organisms were detected in the samples collected at the end of March and beginning of April. Among them: *Bosmina* sp., *Daphnia galeata*, *Cyclops vicinus*, *Thermocyclops vermifer* from spiny crustaceans, and *Polyarthra vulgaris*, *Keratella quadrata*, from spiny crustaceans. Spring zooplankton taxonomically less in Tolimarjon reservoir, in this case *Bosmina* sp (10 thousand pieces/m³) and *Cyclops vicinus* (8 thousand pieces/m³) species made up the main part of the biomass.

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